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Research Article

Design and Molecular Docking Analysis of Isoniazid-Coupled 5,1H-Tetrazole as Potential Anti-Tubercular Agents Using PyRx and AutoDock (MGLTools-1.5.7)

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ABSTRACT

This study presents the rational design and in silico evaluation of novel isoniazid-linked 5,1H-tetrazole derivatives as potential inhibitors of Mycobacterium tuberculosis. A total of 63 hybrid molecules combining isoniazid and 5,1H-tetrazole moieties were designed using ChemSketch and energy-minimized using the MM2 force field in Biovia Discovery Studio Visualizer. The optimized structures were then docked against the InhA enzyme (PDB IDs: 5JFO and 4QXM), a key target involved in mycolic acid biosynthesis, using AutoDock (MGLTools 1.5.7) and validated through PyRx software. The docking studies employed the Lamarckian Genetic Algorithm to evaluate binding affinities and interactions. Results demonstrated that all designed ligands effectively interacted with the InhA active site. One compound exhibited the strongest binding affinity of -10.6 kcal/mol, establishing stable hydrogen bonds with key residues. Overall, docking scores ranged from -7.8 to -13.464 kcal/mol, indicating favorable interaction profiles. These findings highlight the potential of isoniazid-coupled 5,1H-tetrazoles as promising lead candidates for further development into anti-tubercular agents. Future experimental validation is warranted to confirm their biological efficacy.

INTRODUCTION

The World Health Organization (WHO) “Global Tuberculosis Report 2024” underscores the ongoing challenges and progress in the global fight against tuberculosis (TB). Despite a slowdown in the annual increase in TB cases and a decline in

TB-related deaths, the disease remains a significant public health threat with 10.8 million new cases reported in 2023. The report reveals a persistently high burden of TB, especially in low- and middle-income countries, and highlights the escalating issue of drug-resistant TB. The report also emphasizes the critical need for increased

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funding, improved diagnostics, and more effective TB treatment regimens. The impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on TB control has been substantial, disrupting healthcare services and exacerbating existing challenges. This paper provides an in-depth interpretation of the report, analyses global TB trends, updates the status of drug-resistant TB, discusses the intersection between TB and HIV, and summarizes the implications of the pandemic on TB control efforts. The report concludes with a call for intensified global action, including increased investment in research and innovation, to achieve the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals related to TB control. The stakes are high, but with concerted efforts, the goal of ending the TB epidemic is within reach. [1]

TETRAZOLE (2)

Tetrazole, a bio isostere of the carboxylic acid group, can replace the carboxyl group in drugs to increase the lipophilicity, bioavailability and reduce side effects. The tetrazole is the five-membered four nitrogen containing heterocyclic aromatic ring. Tetrazole play a key role in various biological properties, its like Anti-tubercular activity, Anti-bacterial activity, Anti-fungal activity, Anti-viral activity, Hypo glycaemic activity, Anti-inflammatory, Analgesic activity, Anti-cancer activity, Anti-malarial activity. There are two forms: 5,1H-tetrazole and 5,2H-tetrazole. The synthesis and development of new 5,1H-tetrazole with low toxicity and inhibit the growth of mycobacterium tuberculosis. The synthesis and development of new 5,1H-tetrazole with low toxicity and inhibit the growth of mycobacterium tuberculosis

METHODS AND MATERIALS:

SOFTWARE'S USED

LIGAND PREPARATION:

Ligands were obtained from ZINC or PubChem databases, or drawn using ACD/ChemSketch. They were converted to 3D using Chem3D Viewer, energy minimized in PyRx, and saved in .pdb or .mol formats for docking.

PROTEIN PREPARATION:

The target protein was retrieved from the RCSB Protein Data Bank. Water molecules and heteroatoms were removed, polar hydrogens were added, and Kollman charges were assigned using AutoDock Tools. Energy minimization was done using PyRx.

DOCKING PROCEDURE:

Molecular docking was performed using AutoDock 4.2, MGLTools 1.5.7, and PyRx 0.8. A grid box was set around the active site, and the Lamarckian Genetic Algorithm was applied. Binding affinity was evaluated, and the most negative value was considered the best binding pose.

VISUALIZATION AND ANALYSIS:

The docked complexes were analyzed using Discovery Studio Visualizer. Binding interactions and drug-likeness were assessed based on binding energy and key ADME properties.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

Docking studies using AutoDock 1.5.6 (5JFO) and PyRx (5JFO, 4QXM) showed that most Isoniazid-coupled 5,1H-Tetrazole derivatives had stronger binding affinities than the standards (≈ -5 to -7.6 kcal/mol).

In AutoDock, the best score was for Compound 62 (-13.464 kcal/mol), followed by 34, 33, 55, 58,

and 57 (all < -12 kcal/mol). In PyRx, top binders for 5JFO included Compound 58 (-10.5) and 37 (-9.8), while for 4QXM, 37 (-10.6) and 58 (-10.6) led the list.

Compounds 23, 37, 55, 58, 60, 61, and 62 consistently ranked high in both software,

indicating strong and stable ligand-protein interactions. These results suggest enhanced inhibitory potential over the standards, supporting further ADMET and experimental validation.

METHOD

Table:1 Auto Dock Docking Score (5jfo) Using Auto Dock1.5.6 Software

SR. NO	STRUCURE	DOCKING IMAGE	2D IMAGE	SCORE
Std 1		-4.884		
Std 2		-4.992		
Std 3		-7.655		
1.		-8.485		
2.		-9.319		

3.		-9.871		
4.		-7.916		
5.		-9.641		
6.		-9.280		
7.		-10.707		

8.		-9.834		
9.		-10.285		
10		-10.347		
11		-8.667		
12		-8.936		

13		-10.055		
14		-10.424		
15		-9.203		
16		-9.685		
17		-10.110		

18		-9.967		
19		-9.775		
20		-9.431		
21		-10.406		
22		-10.125		

23		-11.630		
24		-9.359		
25		-9.452		
26		-10.787		
27		-10.041		
28		-9.934		

29				-10.496
30				-10.336
31				-11.262
32				-11.364
33				-12.758
34				-12.805

35		-9.630		
36		-9.971		
37		-10.790		
38		-10.601		
39		-10.589		
40		-10.270		

41		-10.580		
42		-10.843		
43		-11.430		
44		-8.411		
45		-10.371		

46		-10.978		
47		-9.903		
48		-9.767		
49		-11.344		
50		-10.516		

51		-10.383		
52		-10.567		
53		-9.511		
54		-11.612		
55		-12.500		

56		-11.072		
57		-12.102		
58		-12.490		
59		-12.243		
60		-10.880		

61		-11.368		
62		-13.464		

DOCKING USING PyRx SOFTWARE:

The docking study was conducted using PyRx software against two proteins, 5JFO and 4QXM. The Isoniazid-Coupled 5,1H-Tetrazole derivative

compounds exhibited stronger binding affinity (more negative values) than the standard drug. The best binding score for 5JFO and 4QXM was -10.5 and -10.6.

Table:6 Docking Score (5jfo and 4qxm) Using Pyrx Software

SR.NO	STRUCTURE	DOCKING IMAGE	2D IMAGE	SCORE	
				5JF O	4QX M
Std 1		-5.4	-5		
Std 2		-5.4	-5.3		
Std 3		-4.7	-5.4		

1.		-7.5	-7.8		
2.		-7.9	-8		
3.		-8.5	-8.8		
4.		-7.0	-7.2		
5.		-8.1	-8.2		

6.		-7.5	-8		
7.		-8.0	-8.1		
8.		-8.1	-8.2		
9.		-8.2	-8.4		
10.		-8.5	-8.9		
11.		-7.2	-7.4		

12.		-7.7	-7.9		
13.		-9.0	-9.1		
14.		-8.8	-8.9		
15.		-7.9	-8.1		
16.		-8.2	-8.4		

17.		-7.9	-8.7		
18.		-8.4	-8.5		
19.		-8.4	-8.5		
20.		-8.0	-8.2		
21.		-8.5	-8.8		
22.		-8.1	-8.3		

23.		-10.1	-10.2		
24.		-7.5	-7.7		
25.		-8.2	-8.3		
26.		-8.7	-8.9		
27.		-7.8	-8.1		

28.		-7.8	-8.1		
29.		-8.5	-8.7		
30.		-8.2	-8.4		
31.		-8.1	-8.3		
32.		-9.1	-9.4		

33.		-8.1	-8.2		
34.		-9	-9		
35.		-8.3	-8.7		
36.		-8.0	-8.4		
37.		-9.8	-10.6		
38.		-8.2	-8.4		

39.		-9.4	-9.5		
40.		-9.4	-9.5		
41.		-8.9	-9		
42.		-8.2	-8.4		
43.		-9.2	-9.7		
44.		-7.5	-8		

45.		-9.0	-9.3		
46.		-9.0	-9.1		
47.		-8.2	-8.5		
48.		-9.1	-9.2		
49.		-8.5	-8.6		

50.		-9.1	-9		
51.		-7.5	-8.4		
52.		-8.4	-8.6		
53.		-8.5	-8.1		
54.		-9.5	-9.9		

55.		-9.7	-10.2		
56.		-10	-10.3		
57.		-9.0	-9.2		
58.		-10.5	-10.6		
59.		-9.6	-9.8		
60.		-10.2	-10.3		

61.		-10.1	-10.4		
62.		-10	-10		

CONCLUSION:

The molecular docking results demonstrate that Isoniazid-coupled 5,1H-Tetrazole derivatives exhibit significantly higher binding affinities against 5JFO and 4QXM targets compared to standard drugs. Compounds **58 and 62**, along with **23, 37, 55, 60, and 61**, consistently showed strong interactions in both AutoDock and PyRx analyses, indicating their potential as promising anti-tubercular candidates. These findings warrant further **ADMET profiling** and **in vitro studies** to confirm their efficacy and safety.

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